

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

ОНЛАЙН ПРОТИВ ОФЛАЙН ОБУЧЕНИЯ

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ONLINE VERSUS OFFLINE LEARNING

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Аннотация

В статье подробно рассматриваются преимущества и недостатки офлайн- и онлайн-уроков. В статье проведено сравнение онлайн- и офлайн-уроков и выявлены наиболее характерные особенности. Было отмечено, что успеваемость учеников была бы выше, если бы они видели реакцию, любовь, внимание, сотрудничество и уважение со стороны учителя. Потому что эти положительные черты мотивируют учащихся и оказывают положительное влияние на результаты обучения. Личные отношения в виде уважения, дружбы и сотрудничества складываются в результате офлайн-урока, что чуждо онлайн-уроку. Кроме того, на офлайн-уроках меньше отвлекающих факторов по сравнению с онлайн-обучением. В статье подчеркивается, что хотя онлайн-обучение является экономически эффективным, оно также имеет некоторые недостатки.

Abstract

The article elaborates advantages and disadvantages of offline and online lessons. Online and offline lessons have been compared and the most prominent characteristic features have been revealed in the article. It has been noted that the student performance would be higher if they saw reaction, love, attention, collaboration and respect from the teacher. Because these positive features motivate the students and have a positive impact in learning outcomes. Personal relations as respect, friendship and collaboration develop as a result of offline lesson which is strange to online lessons. Besides there is less distraction in offline lessons while comparing it with online learning. The article underlines that though the online learning is cost-efficient, it has some drawbacks, as well.

Ключевые слова: офлайн-урок, экономичный, доступный, искренность, сотрудничество, внимание.

Keywords: offline lesson, cost-efficient, affordable, sincerity, collaboration, attention, versus.

The teacher cannot be friendly as in traditional form of lesson which often continues with a positive atmosphere. At traditional lessons, the students feel the teacher's sincerity during the lesson from his or her facial mimics and behavior though it is hard to notice this quality in online lessons. Because the teacher usually closes the camera and the students don't see his or her reactions about their lesson performance. The students always feel need to be evaluated by the teacher. If they see indifference by the teacher, the learning outcome will witness a drop which will have a negative impact on students' results. Besides, the students expect respect, reaction, care, attention, collaboration and love from the teacher. Besides, the students expect respect, reaction, care, attention and love from the teacher. When the learners see love and respect, as well as attention and care by the teacher, they get inspired or encouraged and it influences the quality of the acquisition of the assigned materials considerably. If the students don't see these qualities on the teacher's face, they become demotivated and this negative feature reflects itself on student comprehension and performance. The students are not so passionate to listen to what the lecturer says behind the closed camera.

It is essential to mention asynchronous learning which means anytime-anywhere appeal of online learning [2]. This is based on the most characteristic features

of online learning - the flexibility. The time and place of online learning may be suitable or flexible both for students and teachers.

Online learning becomes cost-efficient when the students don't buy stationery such as school-bags, files, copy-books, books, pencils, pens, eraser and the like. If the lesson is online and students study the lessons in online form and works writes on the computers instead of using pens and markers and don't use any sheets of paper, the money spent on education will decline significantly and it is a financial contribution for, particularly, poor families who send 5 or 6 six children to school. In case the education is online, the family economizes the budget. As mentioned above the students are not obliged to buy shoes and garments for school, college or university which would cost expensive and would not be affordable for a low income family. Taking all afore-said ideas into account it is possible to claim that the mean evaluation of world education systems demonstrates that distance education is more affordable than traditional form of learning.

At offline lessons, personal relationships including sincerity, motivation, enthusiasm play an indispensable role in student performance while these positive psychological qualities are not felt in online lesson. For example, when the student answers the questions very

well, the teacher may reward him or her during the lesson process. This gift may be sweets, cakes or a bar of chocolate, a wrist-watch or something else which cannot be presented in online lesson. This reward may cheer up and motivate the students significantly.

The most noticeable positive feature of offline classes is less distraction compared to online learning. As obvious, students' maximum attention span is supposed to be 10-15 minutes. In offline lessons, this duration may extend due to strong focus on the lesson while it is impossible to focus on the lesson in online lessons so much. In universities of high quality, the students want prefer offline lessons. Since there is better classroom interaction and understanding there which are not found in online lessons.

Another prevalence of offline education is that there is student-student and teacher-student interaction both during and after classes. Personal relations as respect, friendship and collaboration develop in the process of offline lesson which is strange to online lessons. The well-known educational theorist John Dewey argued that learning occurs in collaboration with knowledgeable others [1].

Furthermore, student competition increases in offline lessons which we can't claim it for online lessons. For example, when the teacher asks a question and the student answers it, the teacher asks the students to raise hands who knows the answer. And the student who raises hand first answers the question and gets evaluated. To fulfil this process in the online lesson is impossible, because the teacher may not see all the students in the camera simultaneously and it has a negative impact on student competition. When there is no competition, the quality of the lesson comprehension dips. In offline lessons, the teacher may organize a quiz, or a competition and divide the students into several groups. Unfortunately, the teacher cannot do it in online lesson. Because there is not space concept in online lesson and the views of all students merge in the camera. Piaget's

constructivist theory of learning highlighted the importance of engaged learning where meaningful discussions were held between peers [3].

Extra-curricular activities are not found in online lessons which would be much better for students if they were carried out. The teacher and students may organize an event collaboratively after the lessons. The event may be in relation with commemoration of national heroes or other state level holidays. It is a pity that such activities cannot be conducted online. Social interaction is another important factor in student performance. The sociologist Lev Vygotsky also emphasized the importance of social interaction in learning [4, p.105].

Practice-based learning cannot be implemented successfully in online lessons which contain a lot of exercise as a home task. The students usually have copy-books or note-books at offline lessons and they note down the most important details or information in them and the teacher check and observe each student's writing skills and wants to know if they have comprehended the lesson properly. In online lesson, this supervision over the students is very weak.

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